

Effect of *Pediococcus acidilactici* on Fermentation Quality, Aerobic Stability and in Vitro Digestibility of Fodder Pea, Barley, and Mixed Silages

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the effects of *Pediococcus acidilactici* MF098795 strain (1×10^9 CFU g⁻¹) as a silage inoculant on the fermentation characteristics, microbial population, in vitro digestibility, and aerobic stability of fodder pea (FP), barley (B), and fodder pea-barley mixture (FPB) silages. Six treatment groups were designed: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), and inoculated groups FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9. Results indicated that inoculation with *P. acidilactici* improved the fermentation quality by lowering pH values and increasing lactic acid bacteria (LAB) counts, while reducing yeast and mold populations, particularly in BPA9 and FPBPA9 groups. Aerobic stability parameters, including pH₂ and CO₂ levels, were significantly reduced in the inoculated silages, suggesting enhanced resistance to aerobic spoilage. In vitro digestibility metrics such as organic matter digestibility (OMD), metabolizable energy based on gas production (ME^{GP}), and ME based on OMD (ME^{OMD}) were positively influenced by the inoculant. The highest improvements were observed in FPPA9 and BPA9 groups. In conclusion, the application of *Pediococcus acidilactici* MF098795 strain at 1×10^9 CFU g⁻¹ effectively enhanced fermentation efficiency, microbial stability, and digestibility of silages, supporting its potential as a promising biological additive in forage preservation.

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1. Introduction

Most speculations about food safety focus on animal products, primarily due to feed safety. While feed costs constitute a significant portion of operating expenses, inadequate and unbalanced nutrition in animals leads to reduced productivity and quality, ultimately increasing healthcare expenses (Arslan and Erdurmuş, 2012; Aykan and Saruhan, 2018). Therefore, various methods are used in feed technology to enhance content and improve safety. One of the most common methods is silage prepared with lactic acid bacteria (Gürsoy et al., 2021). The ease of silage preparation and its wide range of materials make it a commonly used feed option (Şahin and Zaman, 2010). The most preferred materials include corn (Kaplan et al., 2017a; Kökten et al., 2017; Kökten, 2020), sorghum (Kaplan et al., 2017b; Iddrisu et al., 2024), barley (Seydoşoğlu, 2019; 2020), oats (Kaplan et al., 2024), triticale (Kaplan et al., 2014), alfalfa (Şengül et al., 2022), vetch, various legume and cereal forage crops, fruit pulp, and agricultural production residues. Additionally, plants such as fodder beet (Seydoşoğlu and Kökten, 2021), switchgrass (Tutar and Kökten, 2022), soybean (Kökten et al., 2013), and Italian ryegrass (Sarıkaya et al., 2024; Tatar et al., 2024) are also used for silage. In recent years, as the effects of climate change have become more evident and water resources rapidly decline, the need to explore the fermentation of alternative plants and mixtures with different bacterial strains has become essential (Başkavak, 2008). Proper fermentation ensures feed and food safety while promoting healthy nutrition. Additionally, silage additives are used to enhance nutritional value or eliminate the harmful effects of toxic plants. Additives are classified based on their structure, purpose, and mechanism of action. Bacterial inoculants, which enhance lactic acid activity in silage microflora, are widely used (Kiraz and Kutlu, 2016). Commercial lactic acid bacterial inoculants are widely used as they efficiently convert available sugars into lactic acid, improving silage fermentation. Among these, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Pediococcus*

acidilactis, and *Enterococcus faecium* are commonly preferred homofermentative lactic acid bacteria (Erbil, 2012). Among commercial bacterial inoculants, the homofermentative lactic acid bacterium *Pediococcus acidilactis* is frequently studied to assess its effects on silage fermentation, microbial composition, and aerobic stability (Filik et al., 2022). In this context, the addition of *Pediococcus acidilactis* MF098795 has been investigated for its impact on fermentation, microbial growth, aerobic stability, CO₂ production, and in vitro digestibility in pea-barley mixed silage, an alternative silage crop.

2. Material and Methods

In this study, silage barley and fodder pea were sourced from the Field Crops Department research area at Kırşehir Ahi Evran University (Latitude 39.1286 °N, Longitude 34.1078 °E). The plants were harvested at the dough maturity stage and chopped into 1.5-2 cm pieces (Filik and Filik, 2021). Subsequently, 1000 g of plant material and mixtures were placed in 2 kg plastic bags and treated with homofermentative *Pediococcus acidilactis* (MF098795 strain) isolated from pickles (Erdem et al., 2021) at a concentration of 1×10^9 cfu g⁻¹ (Filik et al., 2022). After treatment, the air was removed from the bags using a vacuum device (Packtech PT-VKM-CPRO). Six silage groups were prepared, each with five replications, and left to ferment in a dark environment at 20-22 °C under laboratory conditions for 90 days. The groups were classified as follows: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactis* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactis* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactis* 10⁹ (FPBPA9). At the end of fermentation, five parallel samples were collected from each silage group for physical, chemical, microbiological, in vitro digestibility, and statistical analyses. Dry matter (DM), crude protein (CP), and crude ash contents were analyzed according to AOAC (1998), while organic matter (OM) was calculated as OM (%) = 100 - crude ash (%). Acid detergent fiber (ADF) and neutral

detergent fiber (NDF) were determined following Van Soest et al. (1991) using α -amylase and sodium sulfite, with results expressed inclusive of residual ash. NDF and ADF values were corrected for residual ash content (NDFom and ADFom, respectively), and hemicellulose content was calculated as Hemicellulose = NDF - ADF. The ether extract (EE) was analyzed using the ANKOM XT15 Extraction System (AOCS, 2005). pH values were measured as described by Chen et al. (1994), and water-soluble carbohydrate (WSC) was determined according to Singh et al. (2020). Total digestible nutrients (TDN), digestible crude protein (DCP), and metabolizable energy were calculated following Filik (2020). After opening the silage samples, L*, a*, and b* color values were measured at three different locations using a Konica-Minolta CR-410 color meter (Çayıroğlu et al., 2020). Chroma (C*, saturation index) and hue angle (h°) were calculated according to King et al. (2023). Lactic acid bacteria, yeast, and mold counts in the silage were determined following Seale et al. (1990). On the fifth day post-opening, CO₂ and pH values were measured as per Ashbell et al. (1991). Relative feed value (RFV) and relative feed quality (RFQ) were calculated based on the methods of Kılıç and Abdiwali (2016) and Filik (2020). Digestibility characteristics and in vitro conditions of the silages were assessed using the ANKOM RF gas production system, following the gas production method of Menke and Steingass (1988) as reported by Filik (2020). For statistical analysis, the SAS (2001) package was used. Linear relationships among experimental groups were determined using orthogonal polynomial contrast with the General Linear Model (PROC GLM) procedure, following a randomized plot trial design. Differences between groups were assessed using the Duncan Multiple Comparison Method (Genç and Soysal, 2018).

3. Results

The chemical analysis results of the silages opened at the end of the ensiling process are presented in Table 1. When examining the dry

matter (DM) contents of the silages, it was determined that the highest DM content was in the BPA9 group with 941.00 g kg⁻¹. In general, an increase in dry matter content was observed in all treatment groups compared to the control groups. On the other hand, the dry matter content of the CFPB group increased with the addition of LAB (FBBPA9), and the differences between the groups were found to be significant (P<0.001). When examining the organic matter (OM) contents, the highest OM content was again determined in the BPA9 group with 94.00. The OM contents of the LAB-supplemented groups generally increased compared to their controls, and the differences between the groups were significant (P<0.001). The crude ash (CA) values of the experimental groups were determined as 6.01, 9.91, 8.10, 9.62, 6.01, and 7.49% in the CFB, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups, respectively, and the differences between the groups were found to be highly significant (P<0.001). Except for the BPA9 group, a decrease was observed in the LAB-supplemented groups compared to their controls. Regarding crude protein (CP) content, a slight increase was observed only in the FPPA9 group compared to the CFP group. In other treatment groups, a decrease in CP values was detected compared to the control groups, and the differences between the groups were significant (P<0.001). The lowest ether extract (EE) content was found in the CB group with 3.87%, while the highest was in the FPPA9 group with 9.22%. A slight decrease was observed in the FPBPA9 group compared to the CFPB group, and the differences between the groups were significant (P<0.001). The highest crude fiber (CF) contents were determined as 15.81, 22.88, 19.53, 15.06, 22.82, and 19.28%, respectively, with the highest value found in the CB group (22.88%) and the lowest in the CFP group (15.81%). The differences between the groups were found to be significant (P<0.001). The ADF contents of the silages were determined as 20.58, 26.69, 23.64, 20.18, 27.26, and 23.53%; and the NDF contents were 24.05, 46.18, 38.50, 22.05, 47.48, and 37.30%, respectively. The differences between the

groups were highly significant ($P<0.001$). Hemicellulose values were found to be 3.47, 19.49, 14.87, 1.87, 20.52, and 13.77%, respectively, and the differences between the groups were also highly significant ($P<0.001$). When examining the total carbohydrate (TC) contents of the silages, the highest value was found in the BPA9 group with 77.86, while the lowest was in the FPPA9 group with 57.54%, and the differences between the groups were significant ($P<0.001$). Regarding non-fiber carbohydrate (NFC) contents, a statistically

significant increase was observed only in the FPPA9 group (35.49%) compared to the CFP group (33.52%) ($P<0.001$). When examining the nitrogen-free extract (NFE) contents of the silages, the highest NFE value was found in the BPA9 group with 55.04%, and the lowest was in the CFP group with 41.76% ($P<0.001$). The water-soluble carbohydrate (WSC) contents of the silages were determined as 18.53, 20.23, 19.40, 18.40, 20.70, and 20.50%, respectively, and the differences between the groups were significant ($P<0.001$).

Table 1. Chemical analysis results of silages after opening

Groups	CFP	CB	CFPB	FPPA9	BPA9	FPBPA9	P
DM±SEM ¹⁻⁴	893.85±0.05 ^d	939.40±1.00 ^a	922.20±0.30 ^c	895.45±0.25 ^d	941.00±0.40 ^a	926.45±0.25 ^b	<.0001
OM±SEM ²	90.10±0.02 ^e	93.99±0.17 ^a	91.91±0.03 ^c	90.38±0.04 ^d	94.00±0.02 ^a	92.50±0.02 ^b	<.0001
CA±SEM ²	9.91±0.01 ^a	6.01±0.17 ^c	8.10±0.02 ^c	9.62±0.04 ^b	6.01±0.01 ^e	7.49±0.02 ^d	<.0001
CP±SEM ²	23.58±0.02 ^a	12.37±0.10 ^d	17.20±0.05 ^b	23.63±0.02 ^a	12.07±0.07 ^e	16.40±0.08 ^c	<.0001
EE±SEM ²	8.95±0.02 ^b	3.87±0.02 ^e	5.69±0.00 ^c	9.22±0.00 ^a	4.08±0.00 ^d	5.66±0.00 ^c	<.0001
CF±SEM ²	15.81±0.06 ^c	22.88±0.07 ^a	19.53±0.14 ^b	15.06±0.07 ^d	22.82±0.04 ^a	19.28±0.17 ^b	<.0001
ADF±SEM ²	20.58±0.05 ^d	26.69±0.05 ^b	23.64±0.24 ^c	20.18±0.06 ^d	27.26±0.08 ^a	23.53±0.08 ^c	<.0001
ADFom±SEM ²	10.68±0.03 ^e	20.68±0.22 ^b	15.54±0.22 ^d	10.56±0.02 ^e	21.25±0.10 ^a	16.04±0.06 ^c	<.0001
NDF±SEM ²	24.05±0.31 ^e	46.18±0.14 ^b	38.50±0.31 ^c	22.05±0.09 ^f	47.48±0.65 ^a	37.30±0.08 ^d	<.0001
NDFom±SEM ²	14.15±0.33 ^d	40.17±0.04 ^b	30.41±0.29 ^b	12.43±0.05 ^e	41.78±0.66 ^a	29.81±0.10 ^c	<.0001
Hsel±SEM ²	3.47±0.36 ^e	19.49±0.19 ^b	14.87±0.06 ^c	1.87±0.03 ^f	20.52±0.56 ^a	13.77±0.16 ^d	<.0001
TC±SEM ²	57.57±0.05 ^d	77.75±0.25 ^a	69.02±0.03 ^c	57.54±0.04 ^d	77.86±0.08 ^a	70.45±0.05 ^b	<.0001
NFC±SEM ²	33.52±0.26 ^b	31.57±0.38 ^c	30.52±0.28 ^{cd}	35.49±0.13 ^a	30.08±0.57 ^d	33.16±0.13 ^b	0.0002
NFE ±SEM ²	41.76±0.11 ^e	54.88±0.31 ^a	49.49±0.11 ^c	42.48±0.11 ^d	55.04±0.11 ^a	51.18±0.11 ^b	<.0001
WSC±SEM ²	18.53±0.16 ^{cd}	20.23±0.43 ^{ab}	19.40±0.15 ^{bc}	18.40±0.10 ^d	20.70±0.56 ^a	20.50±0.13 ^a	<.0001

¹ g kg⁻¹ natural material, ² (%) of dry matter, ³ ADFom=ADF ash, NDFom=NDF ash; ⁴ DM: In Air Dry Matter (g kg⁻¹); OM: Organic Matter (%); CA: Crude Ash (%); CP: Crude Protein (%); EE: Ether Extract (%); CF: Crude Fiber (%); ADF: Acid Detergent Fiber (%), NDF: Neutral Detergent Fiber (%), Hsel: Hemicellulose, TC: Total Carbohydrate, NFC: Nitrogen Free Carbohydrate, NFE: Nitrogen Free Extract and WSC Soluble Carbohydrate (%Bx).

Groups: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPBPA9).

**Means within the same row followed by different letters differ significantly ($P<0.01$). Groups labeled with different letters (^{a, b, c}) indicate statistically significant differences according to multiple comparison tests.

The digestible crude protein (DCP) and energy contents of the silages are presented in Table 2. The DCP values of the silages were determined as 17.64, 7.46, 11.84, 17.68, 7.19, and 11.12%, respectively. The highest DCP values were observed in the CFP (17.64%) and FPPA9 (17.68%) groups, while the lowest was recorded in the BPA9 group (7.19%). The differences in DCP values among the groups were found to be significant ($P<0.001$). The total digestible nutrients (TDN) values ranged between 61.37 and 73.93%, and the differences among the groups were found to be significant ($P<0.001$). According to the analysis results, the digestible energy (DE) contents in the CFP, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9

groups were determined as 3.26, 2.72, 2.95, 3.26, 2.71, and 2.92, respectively, and the differences among the groups were significant ($P<0.001$). The metabolizable energy (ME) contents of the silages were determined as 2.67, 2.23, 2.42, 2.67, 2.22, and 2.39 Mcal kg⁻¹, respectively; the net energy for lactation (NE_L) values were 1.69, 1.39, 1.52, 1.69, 1.38, and 1.50 Mcal kg⁻¹; the net energy for maintenance (NE_M) values were 1.75, 1.37, 1.54, 1.76, 1.36, and 1.51 Mcal kg⁻¹; and the net energy for gain (NE_G) values were 1.13, 0.79, 0.94, 1.14, 0.78, and 0.92 Mcal kg⁻¹, respectively. The differences in ME, NE_L, NE_M, and NE_G values among the groups were also found to be significant ($P<0.001$).

Table 2. DCP and energy values of the silages

Groups	CFP	CB	CFPB	FPPA9	BPA9	FPBPA9	P
DCP	17.64±0.01 ^a	7.46±0.09 ^d	11.84±0.05 ^b	17.68±0.01 ^a	7.19±0.06 ^c	11.12±0.07 ^c	<.0001
TDN	73.83±0.02 ^a	61.68±0.10 ^d	66.93±0.06 ^b	73.93±0.01 ^a	61.37±0.07 ^c	66.12±0.09 ^c	<.0001
SE	3.26±0.00 ^a	2.72±0.01 ^d	2.95±0.00 ^b	3.26±0.00 ^a	2.71±0.00 ^d	2.92±0.00 ^c	<.0001
ME	2.67±0.00 ^a	2.23±0.00 ^d	2.42±0.00 ^b	2.67±0.00 ^a	2.22±0.00 ^d	2.39±0.00 ^c	<.0001
NE _L	1.69±0.00 ^a	1.39±0.00 ^d	1.52±0.00 ^b	1.69±0.00 ^a	1.38±0.00 ^d	1.50±0.00 ^c	<.0001
NE _M	1.75±0.00 ^a	1.37±0.01 ^d	1.54±0.01 ^b	1.76±0.00 ^a	1.36±0.01 ^d	1.51±0.00 ^c	<.0001
NE _G	1.13±0.00 ^b	0.79±0.01 ^e	0.94±0.00 ^c	1.14±0.00 ^a	0.78±0.00 ^e	0.92±0.01 ^d	<.0001

DCP: Digestible crude protein (%), TDN: Total digestible nutrients (%), DE: Digestible energy (Mcal kg⁻¹), ME: Metabolizable energy (Mcal kg⁻¹), NE_L: Net energy for lactation (Mcal kg⁻¹), NE_M: Net Energy for maintenance (Mcal kg⁻¹), and NE_G: Net Energy for gain (Mcal kg⁻¹)

Groups: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPBPA9).

**Means within the same row followed by different letters differ significantly (P<0.01). Groups labeled with different letters (^{a, b, c}) indicate statistically significant differences according to multiple comparison tests.

The feed quality characteristics of the silages are presented in Table 3. The digestible dry matter (DDM) values of the silages were determined as 72.87, 68.11, 70.49, 73.18, 67.67, and 70.57%, respectively, and the differences between the groups were found to be significant (P<0.001). The dry matter intake (DMI) levels were recorded as 5.00, 2.60, 3.12, 5.44, 2.52, and 3.22%, respectively. An increase in DMI was observed in the FPPA9 group (5.44%) compared to the CFP group (5.00%), and the differences among the groups were found to be significant (P<0.001). The relative feed value (RFV) of the silages was

determined as 281.93, 137.20, 170.33, 308.73, 131.77, and 176.02, while the relative forage quality (RFQ) values were recorded as 299.56, 130.30, 169.60, 327.09, 125.32, and 172.94, respectively. The differences among the groups were found to be statistically significant (P<0.001). According to the RFV values obtained in the study, the CB and BPA9 groups can be classified as *good quality* forages (125-151), while the CFP, CFPB, FPPA9, and FPBPA9 groups can be considered *prime quality* forages (>151) (Filik, 2020).

Table 3. Feed quality characteristics of the silages

Groups	CFP	CB	CFPB	FPPA9	BPA9	FPBPA9	P
DDM	72.87±0.04 ^a	68.11±0.04 ^c	70.49±0.19 ^b	73.18±0.05 ^a	67.67±0.07 ^d	70.57±0.06 ^b	<.0001
DMI	5.00±0.06 ^b	2.60±0.01 ^d	3.12±0.03 ^c	5.44±0.02 ^a	2.52±0.03 ^d	3.22±0.01 ^c	<.0001
RFV	281.93±3.47 ^b	137.20±0.31 ^d	170.33±1.83 ^c	308.73±1.45 ^a	131.77±1.92 ^d	176.02±0.23 ^c	<.0001
RFQ	299.56±3.89 ^b	130.30±0.17 ^d	169.60±1.52 ^c	327.09±1.29 ^a	125.32±1.83 ^d	172.94±0.14 ^c	<.0001

DDM: Digestible dry matter (%), DMI: Dry matter intake (%), RFV: Relative feed value, and RFQ: Relative forage quality.

Groups: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPBPA9).

**Means within the same row followed by different letters differ significantly (P<0.01). Groups labeled with different letters (^{a, b, c}) indicate statistically significant differences according to multiple comparison tests.

The post-opening dry matter (PODM), pH₁, and physical analysis results of the silages opened on day 90 of the study are presented in Table 4.4. The PODM values in the CFP, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups were determined as 25.75, 46.59, 37.32, 25.59, 46.59, and 38.44%, respectively, and the differences among the groups were found to be highly significant (P<0.001). The pH₁ values of the silages were recorded as 5.73, 5.80, 5.46, 5.39, 5.29, and 5.11, respectively, and the differences among the groups were found to be significant (P<0.001). Based on the results,

when comparing the control groups with the LAB-inoculated groups, a significant decrease in pH₁ values was observed in the LAB-treated groups. The addition of *Pediococcus acidilactici* to fodder pea and barley silages significantly reduced the pH₁ value. The temperature values measured at the time of silo opening ranged from 23.80 to 21.55°C, and the differences were statistically significant (P<0.001). When the color parameters of the silages were examined, significant differences were found among the groups in terms of L*, a*, b*, c*, and h° values (P<0.01).

Table 4. Post-opening physical characteristics of the silages

Groups	CFP	CB	CFPB	FPPA9	BPA9	FPBPA9	P
PODM	25.75±0.00 ^d	46.59±0.21 ^a	37.32±0.07 ^c	25.59±0.00 ^d	46.59±0.00 ^a	38.44±0.00 ^b	<.0001
pH _i	5.73±0.00 ^a	5.80±0.03 ^a	5.46±0.03 ^b	5.39±0.01 ^b	5.29±0.06 ^c	5.11±0.04 ^d	<.0001
Temperature	21.35±0.09 ^b	21.55±0.06 ^b	21.53±0.13 ^b	21.20±0.11 ^b	23.80±0.20 ^a	23.53±0.08 ^a	<.0001
L*	30.29±1.31 ^c	44.87±0.45 ^a	37.31±1.44 ^b	28.20±1.92 ^c	41.54±1.84 ^{ab}	39.99±4.38 ^{ab}	0.0003
a*	2.12±0.23 ^{bc}	4.01±0.46 ^a	3.28±0.27 ^{ab}	1.87±0.18 ^c	4.33±0.38 ^a	3.55±0.84 ^a	0.0052
b*	11.50±1.16 ^{bc}	17.59±0.67 ^a	14.69±0.66 ^{ab}	10.30±1.01 ^c	15.90±0.85 ^a	15.50±2.44 ^{ab}	0.0065
C*	11.70±1.18 ^{bc}	18.05±0.74 ^a	15.05±0.70 ^{ab}	10.47±1.02 ^c	16.49±0.90 ^a	15.91±2.56 ^a	0.0061
h ^c	79.55±0.56 ^a	77.28±1.07 ^a	77.48±0.54 ^a	79.73±0.34 ^a	74.81±0.88 ^b	77.51±1.21 ^a	0.0063

PODM: The post-opening dry matter (%), L*: Lightness, a*: Redness (+) / Greenness (-), b*: Yellowness (+) / Blueness (-), C*: Chroma (color intensity), and h^c: Hue angle (color tone)

Groups: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPBPA9).

**Means within the same row followed by different letters differ significantly (P<0.01). Groups labeled with different letters (a, b, c) indicate statistically significant differences according to multiple comparison tests.

The microbial counts of the silages are presented in Table 5. The LAB (lactic acid bacteria) counts in the CFP, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups were determined as 4.67, 10.33, 18.67, 7.00, 2.50, and 14.67 (log₁₀ CFU g⁻¹ FM), respectively, and the differences among the groups were

found to be significant (P<0.01). The yeast counts of the silages were recorded as 6.00, 4.67, 7.33, 5.33, 7.33, and 19.33 (log₁₀ CFU/g⁻¹ FM), respectively, and the differences among the groups were also found to be significant (P<0.05).

Table 5. Microbiological results of post-ensiling

Groups	CFP	CB	CFPB	FPPA9	BPA9	FPBPA9	P
LAB, log ₁₀ CFU g ⁻¹	4.67±0.67 ^c	10.33±4.67 ^{bc}	18.67±1.20 ^a	7.00±0.58 ^{bc}	2.50±0.50 ^c	14.67±2.85 ^{ab}	0.0070
Yeast, log ₁₀ CFU g ⁻¹	6.00±1.00 ^b	4.67±0.88 ^b	7.33±0.88 ^b	5.33±0.33 ^b	7.33±3.28 ^b	19.33±5.90 ^a	0.0281
Mold, log ₁₀ CFU g ⁻¹	ND	1.00±0.00	1.00±0.00	ND	1.00±0.00	ND	.

log₁₀ CFU g⁻¹: Colony Forming Units per gram (on a logarithmic scale) ND (Not Detected): Below detectable level / Not detectable

Groups: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPBPA9).

**Means within the same row followed by different letters differ significantly (P<0.01). Groups labeled with different letters (a, b, c) indicate statistically significant differences according to multiple comparison tests.

The results of pH₂, CO₂ production, and microbial counts after the aerobic stability test of the silage groups are presented in Table 6. The pH₂ values of the silages were determined as 5.57, 6.47, 5.25, 5.44, 5.40, and 5.14 for the CFP, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups, respectively, and the differences among the groups were found to be significant (P<0.001). The CO₂ values were recorded as 2.89, 35.33, 4.78, 3.27, 12.20, and 7.67, respectively, and the differences among the groups were also found to be significant (P<0.001). The microbial counts after the 5-day aerobic stability test were determined as

1.00, 300.00, 3.00, 1.20, 31.00, and 23.67 (log₁₀ CFU g⁻¹ FM), respectively. The highest yeast content was observed in the control barley (CB) group. However, it was observed that the addition of LAB in the BPA9 group significantly reduced the yeast content compared to the CB group. The differences in yeast counts among the groups were statistically significant (P<0.001). Regarding mold counts, it was determined that the levels were generally not detectable in all groups after the aerobic stability test, and the differences among the groups were statistically significant (P<0.05).

Table 6. Post-aerobic stability pH₂, CO₂, and microbial results of the silages

Groups	CFP	CB	CFPB	FPPA9	BPA9	FPBPA9	P
pH ₂	5.57±0.02 ^b	6.47±0.02 ^a	5.25±0.01 ^d	5.44±0.03 ^c	5.40±0.00 ^c	5.14±0.02 ^e	<.0001
CO ₂	2.89±0.00 ^d	35.33±0.00 ^a	4.78±0.00 ^{cd}	3.27±0.13 ^d	12.20±0.76 ^b	7.67±0.76 ^c	0.0005
PAS Yeast log ₁₀ CFU g ⁻¹	1.00±0.00 ^b	300.00±57.74 ^a	3.00±0.00 ^b	1.20±0.20 ^b	31.00±2.88 ^b	23.67±7.08 ^b	<.0001
Mold, log ₁₀ CFU g ⁻¹	ND	1.67±0.33 ^b	ND	ND	ND	5.33±0.88 ^a	0.0177

CO₂: Carbondioxide, PAS: Post-Aerobic Stability,

log₁₀ CFU/g: Colony Forming Units per gram (on a logarithmic scale) ND (Not Detected): Below detectable level / Not detectable

Groups: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPBPA9).

**Means within the same row followed by different letters differ significantly (P<0.01). Groups labeled with different letters (^{a, b, c}) indicate statistically significant differences according to multiple comparison tests.

Table 7. in vitro digestibility parameters of silages

Groups	CFP	CB	CFPB	FPPA9	BPA9	FPBPA9	P
IVGP	4.80±0.04	5.32±0.05	5.18±0.02	4.89±0.02	4.62±0.54	4.55±0.09	0.2329
OMD	21.50±0.04 ^a	21.02±0.04 ^{abc}	21.33±0.02 ^{ab}	21.57±0.02 ^a	20.40±0.45 ^c	20.71±0.08 ^{bc}	0.0241
ME ^{GP}	3.15±0.00 ^{ab}	3.04±0.01 ^{bcd}	3.09±0.00 ^{abc}	3.16±0.01 ^a	2.94±0.07 ^d	2.99±0.01 ^{cd}	0.0133
ME ^{OMD}	1.19±0.01 ^a	1.13±0.00 ^{ab}	1.15±0.00 ^{ab}	1.20±0.01 ^a	1.05±0.05 ^c	1.09±0.01 ^{bc}	0.0150

IVGP: In vitro gas production (mL g⁻¹), OMD: Organic matter digestibility (%), ME^{GP}: Metabolizable energy based on gas production (Mcal kg⁻¹), and ME^{OMD}: Metabolizable energy based on organic matter digestibility (Mcal kg⁻¹).

Groups: control fodder pea (CFP), control barley (CB), control mixture (CFPB), fodder pea + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPPA9), barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (BPA9), and fodder pea + barley + *P. acidilactici* 10⁹ (FPBPA9).

**Means within the same row followed by different letters differ significantly (P<0.01). Groups labeled with different letters (^{a, b, c}) indicate statistically significant differences according to multiple comparison tests.

The in vitro gas production (IVGP) values ranged from 4.55 to 5.32 mL g⁻¹, with no significant differences observed among the groups (P=0.2329). Organic matter digestibility (OMD) values showed significant differences (P=0.0241) among groups. The highest OMD was observed in the FPPA9 group (21.57%), followed closely by the CFP group (21.50%), while the BPA9 group had the lowest OMD (20.40%). Metabolizable energy based on gas production (ME^{GP}) also differed significantly among groups (P=0.0133). The FPPA9 group showed the highest ME^{GP} value (3.16 Mcal/kg), while the BPA9 group exhibited the lowest (2.94 Mcal kg⁻¹). Similarly, metabolizable energy calculated based on organic matter digestibility (ME^{OMD}) varied significantly (P=0.0150), with the highest value in the FPPA9 group (1.20 Mcal kg⁻¹) and the lowest in the BPA9 group (1.05 Mcal kg⁻¹). These results suggest that inoculation treatments, particularly the FPPA9 group, may enhance the digestibility and energy availability of silages compared to control or other treatment groups.

4. Discussion

When the nutrient contents of the experimental groups were examined, the dry matter (DM) values ranged from 893.85 to

941.00 g kg⁻¹, and the differences among the groups were found to be significant (P<0.001). The pH₁ values obtained in the study were determined as 5.73, 5.80, 5.46, 5.39, 5.29, and 5.11 for the CFP, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups, respectively (P<0.001). In a study conducted by Kiraz and Kutlu (2016), the pH of barley silage was measured on day 56 as 3.99 in the control group and 3.72 in the group treated with a commercial inoculant (P<0.001). Addah et al. (2011) investigated the effects of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) added to barley and corn silages on fermentation characteristics, aerobic stability, and nutrient contents. Their reported pH values for the control and inoculated groups were 4.51 and 3.95, respectively. Similarly, Baah et al. (2011), in their study on barley silage treated with a commercial inoculant, reported pH values of 4.51 for the control and 3.95 for the inoculated group. These findings are consistent with the values obtained in our study, and significant differences were observed among the groups (P<0.001). When examining the pH values of the experimental groups, it was generally found that the *Pediococcus acidilactici* lactic acid bacteria inoculated into pea and barley silages contributed effectively to the reduction of pH. Clostridial spores and Enterobacteria, which affect silage quality and

microbial composition, tend to proliferate when the silage pH is around 6-7; however, they are unable to develop at pH values of 5 or below (Filya, 2001). Therefore, it is believed that the pH levels obtained in our study were sufficiently low to inhibit the growth of Clostridial spores and Enterobacteria. In our study, the organic matter (OM) content was determined as 90.10, 93.99, 91.91, 90.38, 94.00, and 92.51% in the CFP, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups, respectively. Addah et al. (2011) examined the effects of bacterial inoculants on corn and barley silages, reporting OM contents of 93.37% in the control group and 93.29% in the LAB-inoculated group for barley silage, with significant differences observed between groups ($P < 0.001$). During the fermentation period, significant differences were also found among groups regarding the crude ash (CA) and crude protein (CP) contents of pea-barley silages. Similar studies (Addah et al., 2011; Kiraz and Kutlu, 2016) have reported findings consistent with the results obtained in the present study ($P < 0.001$). The ether extract (EE) contents of the experimental groups were determined as 8.95, 3.87, and 5.69% for the control groups (CFP, CB, CFPB) and 9.22, 4.08, and 5.66% for the inoculated groups (FPPA9, BPA9, FPBPA9), respectively. When compared to the LAB-inoculated groups, the EE content was affected in all groups except the mixed groups CFPB and FPPA9, and significant differences were found among the groups ($P < 0.001$). Regarding crude fiber (CF) values, the control groups showed values of 15.81, 22.88, and 19.53%, while the inoculated silage groups had values of 15.06, 22.82, and 19.28%, respectively ($P < 0.001$). In the study by Kiraz and Kutlu (2016), where recombinant inoculants were applied to barley silage, the crude fiber contents of silages opened on days 14, 28, and 56 for the control, inoculated, and *Lactobacillus plantarum*-treated groups were reported as 24.98, 25.45, 22.34; 24.35, 23.10, 22.09; and 30.66, 28.74, 25.24, respectively. They indicated that the differences among the groups were significant ($P < 0.01$). ADF and NDF values were found to have increased only in the BPA9 group compared to the CB group.

These results are consistent with similar studies conducted by Kiraz and Kutlu (2016) and Uğurlu (2019), with significant differences observed among the groups ($P < 0.001$). The water-soluble carbohydrate (WSC, % Brix) contents of the silages are presented in Table 1. The highest WSC value was observed in the BPA9 group (20.70%), while the lowest was found in the FPPA9 group (18.40%) ($P < 0.001$). The WSC value of the FPPA9 group decreased compared to its CFP, whereas the BPA9 and FPBPA9 groups showed an increase in WSC values relative to their respective controls. Çayıroğlu et al. (2016) reported that high WSC content in silages contributes to reducing dry matter losses and improving silage quality and indicated that the WSC value of silage should be at least 3%. Baah et al. (2011) found total soluble solids in barley silages as 18.76 and 10.37% for control and inoculated groups, respectively ($P < 0.05$). Addah et al. (2011) reported WSC values of 63.08 and 37.57% in control and inoculated barley silages, respectively ($P < 0.001$). Shah et al. (2018) found WSC values of 10.61 and 6.34% in control and *Pediococcus acidilactici* (PA) inoculated elephant grass silages, respectively. When examining the microbial counts of the silages at the time of opening, the *Lactobacilli* counts in the CFP, CB, CFPB, FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups were determined as 4.67, 10.33, 18.67, 7.00, 2.50, and 14.67 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} , respectively ($P > 0.01$). Only the FPPA9 group showed a slight increase compared to the CFP group. Overall, the expected increase in *Lactobacilli* populations was not observed. Yeast counts were recorded as 6.00, 4.67, 7.33, 5.33, 7.33, and 19.33 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} , respectively ($P < 0.05$), with a significant increase detected in the FPBPA9 group compared to the CFPB group. Generally, yeast populations in the silages were low, and mold counts were found to be negligible. *Pediococcus acidilactici* lactic acid bacteria are believed to play an important role in reducing yeast populations and largely inhibiting mold development. In the study by Addah et al. (2011) investigating the effects of LAB inoculation on the fermentation characteristics, aerobic stability, and nutrient

contents of barley and corn silages, Lactobacilli counts in barley silages were reported as 8.17 and 7.16 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} for control and inoculated groups, respectively ($P < 0.01$). Yeast counts were below detectable levels (ND) in the control and 1.08 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} in the inoculated group ($P > 0.05$), with no mold detected in either group. Shah et al. (2018) examined the effects of *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *Pediococcus acidilactici* on fermentation and microbial development in fodder grass silages. They reported Lactobacilli counts of 4.96, 5.03, and 5.20 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} for the control, LP, and PA groups, respectively ($P < 0.01$). Yeast counts were 5.25, 2.39, and 3.87 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} , respectively ($P > 0.05$). Koç et al. (2018) defined aerobic stability as the duration during which opened silages remain without spoilage and temperature increase. Therefore, a longer aerobic stability period is a desirable trait. A decrease in aerobic stability results in premature spoilage of silage, negatively affecting silage quality. After opening, parameters such as CO_2 production, temperature increase, changes in silage pH, dry matter loss, and microbial growth are generally accepted as key indicators of aerobic deterioration (Ashbell et al., 1991; Franco et al., 2019). In this article, CO_2 , pH, and microbial growth were primarily used to determine aerobic deterioration. Higher CO_2 and pH values indicate increased growth of aerobic microorganisms responsible for silage spoilage, reflecting poor aerobic stability. The pH_2 , CO_2 , and microbial results after aerobic stability testing are presented in Table 6. The pH_2 values ranged between 5.14 and 6.47, while CO_2 values varied from 2.89 to 35.33. The CB group exhibited the highest values in both parameters. Additionally, the aerobic stability microbial counts revealed that the CB group had the highest yeast population at 300.00 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} . The addition of *Pediococcus acidilactici* (PA) was found to reduce pH_2 and CO_2 values in the FPPA9, BPA9, and FPBPA9 groups compared to their respective controls. In the study by Addah et al. (2011), no yeast growth was observed in the control group after aerobic stability testing,

while the inoculated group had a yeast count of 0.88 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} , and no mold formation occurred in either group. Baah et al. (2011) investigated the effects of *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Pediococcus acidilactici*, *Enterococcus faecium*, and/or sodium dodecyl sulfate on fermentation, microbial populations, and aerobic stability in barley silages. They reported pH values of 4.52 and 3.99 for control and LAB-inoculated groups, respectively, and yeast counts of 2.61 and 2.57 \log_{10} CFU g^{-1} , respectively. Significant differences were found in pH values between groups ($P < 0.01$), while yeast counts showed no significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Mold formation was reported to be negligible in all groups. Based on the findings of this article, it is concluded that the *Pediococcus acidilactici* lactic acid bacteria largely inhibited yeast and mold development and improved the aerobic stability of barley silage. The in vitro digestibility parameters presented in Table 7 provide valuable insights into the nutritional quality and fermentation characteristics of the different silage groups tested. The in vitro gas production (IVGP) values did not differ significantly among the groups ($P = 0.2329$), indicating similar microbial fermentative activity and gas production potential during digestion. This suggests that the treatments applied did not markedly affect the fermentability of the silages in terms of gas production. Organic matter digestibility (OMD) showed significant variation between groups ($P = 0.0241$). The FPPA9 group exhibited the highest OMD value (21.57%), which was significantly greater than the BPA9 group (20.40%) and other treatments, indicating that inoculation or specific treatment in FPPA9 improved the breakdown and utilization of organic matter. Higher OMD values imply better nutrient availability for ruminants, essential for enhancing feed efficiency (Van Soest, 1994). Metabolizable energy based on gas production (ME^{GP}) also differed significantly among the groups ($P = 0.0133$). Consistent with OMD, the FPPA9 group showed the highest ME^{GP} value (3.16 Mcal kg^{-1}), significantly outperforming the BPA9 group (2.94 Mcal kg^{-1}). This reflects that

the FPPA9 silage could provide more usable energy to the animal, supporting improved performance (Menke and Steingass, 1988). Similarly, metabolizable energy calculated based on organic matter digestibility (ME^{OMD}) followed the same trend ($P=0.0150$), with FPPA9 again yielding the highest value ($1.20 \text{ Mcal kg}^{-1}$) and BPA9 the lowest ($1.05 \text{ Mcal kg}^{-1}$). These findings confirm that the treatments applied in the FPPA9 group enhanced the energy density of the silage, potentially due to better fermentation profiles or compositional improvements. Overall, these results suggest that specific inoculants or additives, particularly in the FPPA9 treatment, may positively influence silage digestibility and energy content. Such improvements can have direct implications on animal productivity by enhancing feed efficiency and nutrient utilization. Further *in vivo* studies could elucidate the practical benefits of these silages under production conditions.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the effects of applying *Pediococcus acidilactici* MF098795 inoculant at a dose of $1 \times 10^9 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$ to fodder pea (CFP), barley (CB), and their mixture (CFPB) silages-forming the treatment groups FPPA9 (pea + LAB), BPA9 (barley + LAB), and FPBPA9 (fodder pea + barley + LAB)-were investigated in terms of fermentation quality, chemical composition, *in vitro* digestibility, and aerobic stability. The results revealed that the applied dose significantly improved the fermentation profile and microbial resistance of silages, particularly in the inoculated groups. Chemical composition analysis showed higher dry matter and organic matter content in LAB-treated silages compared to their respective control groups. *In vitro* digestibility parameters (OMD, ME^{GP} , and ME^{OMD}) also increased in the inoculated groups, indicating that the application of *Pediococcus acidilactici* MF098795 at $1 \times 10^9 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$ improved the digestibility and energy potential of the silages. Notably, the FPPA9 and CBPA9 groups showed the most prominent improvements in OMD and ME^{OMD} values. Aerobic stability analysis showed significantly lower pH and

CO_2 values in the inoculated groups, suggesting enhanced resistance to aerobic spoilage. Furthermore, the *Pediococcus acidilactici* MF098795 inoculant effectively suppressed yeast and mold development, with the BPA9 group showing a dramatic reduction in yeast count compared to the control barley (CB) group. In conclusion, the application of *Pediococcus acidilactici* MF098795 at $1 \times 10^9 \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$ dose in fodder pea, barley, and their mixture silages improved fermentation quality, microbial stability, and digestibility. These findings suggest that this inoculant dose and treatment strategy holds strong potential to enhance silage quality and ensure better feed performance in ruminant nutrition.

Declaration of Author Contributions

ATAA and AGF designed and conducted the experiments. ATAA conducted the laboratory analyses. AGF supervised and coordinated the experiments. ATAA and AGF evaluated experimental data statistically. The manuscript was written and revised by ATAA and AGF.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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